

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D2.4 Persistent Identifiers in Action: System Integrations Supporting FAIR Workflows

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Executive summary

The Implementing FAIR Workflows project is a 3-year project to implement exemplar FAIR workflows in cognitive neuroscience research, based on the existing persistent identifier (PID) and metadata infrastructure. Open scholarly infrastructure, pivotal to FAIR research practices, relies on the integration of PIDs and metadata across various research tools and systems, which are essential for identifying a wider range of research outputs, enriching the corpus of open metadata, and creating meaningful links among entities in the research ecosystem. The implementation of these integrations demands a nuanced approach to fit within existing workflows, minimizing disruption and optimizing user experience.

The report collates experiences from project partners within the FAIR Workflows project. CEDAR's integration allows users to create Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for metadata templates and instances, enhancing domain metadata quality and visibility and enabling connections to other research outputs; ChronosHub enabled streamlined data sharing by integrating with DataCite API to suggest relevant datasets and prompt data deposition in the manuscript submission process; DMPTool has evolved to enable researchers to link their research outputs directly to their data management plans, making these plans more dynamic and interconnected with the research lifecycle; Dryad's integration with the CEDAR Embeddable Editor enables researchers to select and fill out appropriate metadata templates during data deposition, linking these templates to the datasets via DOIs; and RAiD focuses on creating a flexible PID system for research projects, incorporating a comprehensive metadata schema for linking various research activities and outputs.

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Introduction

Open scholarly infrastructure, particularly Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and metadata, underpins an open and FAIR research ecosystem¹. However, the value of PIDs and metadata only manifests when seamlessly integrated into the diverse systems and tools employed by stakeholders throughout the research lifecycle. PIDs can be integrated into different types of systems, including grant management systems utilized by funders and awardees, data management plan authoring platforms and data repositories managed by research managers and scientists, and specialized research supporting systems like metadata template workbenches. Such an interconnected ecosystem enhances the efficiency of scholarly workflows and ultimately contributes to the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR).

Goals of Integration

The integration of open scholarly infrastructure serves three pivotal goals, each contributing to the overarching aim of making research more FAIR.

1. Identifying all research outputs: Integration enables the identification and incorporation of different types of research outputs, e.g. datasets, code, preregistrations, etc., beyond traditional publications, acknowledging the diverse forms research can take.
2. Enriching the corpus of open metadata: By integrating PIDs and metadata workflows within and across tools and platforms to promote data-sharing best practices, there is a deliberate effort to enrich open and standardized metadata.
3. Creating links among related entities: Integration fosters the creation of meaningful links between various entities in the research ecosystem, building a comprehensive and interconnected record of knowledge.

Implementing Seamless Integration

The implementation of integration necessitates a nuanced approach, acknowledging the intricacies of existing workflows and ensuring minimal disruption for users. This involves the creation of bespoke workflows within local systems, identifying where within the existing workflow an entity or relationship should be captured, determining relevant metadata values, and establishing meaningful connections. The ultimate aim is to seamlessly embed PIDs and metadata workflows into everyday research practices without imposing an undue burden on users.

¹ Cousijn, H., Braukmann, R., Fenner, M., Ferguson, C., van Horik, R., Lammey, R., Meadows, A., & Lambert, S. (2021). Connected Research: The Potential of the PID Graph. *Patterns*, 2(1), 100180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2020.100180>

Project Partners' Integration Experiences

This report documents the work of project partners who have successfully implemented PIDs and metadata workflows in their systems. Through detailed descriptions and demonstrations, these partners explain their integration processes, outlining the features that support PID registration and metadata creation workflows. They also share valuable lessons learned, shedding light on challenges overcome and strategies employed.

The report serves as a reference for future implementers, offering practical guidance and technical documentation. It provides examples for those seeking to integrate PIDs into their own systems, fostering a more interconnected and FAIR research landscape.

Integrations

DMP Tool

The DMP Tool was developed from a grassroots effort of eight institutions beginning in January 2011. These institutions came together in direct response to demands from funding agencies, such as the National Science Foundation (NSF), that researchers plan to manage their research data. The DMP Tool was developed in an effort to consolidate expertise and reduce costs in addressing data management needs at their respective institutions. This original mission still serves as the guiding principle of the DMP Tool as the application continues to be free and community-supported.

Recent feature developments have focused on transforming the DMP from a static text file into an interoperable, networked hub of information wherein details about a research project can be updated and queried over the project's lifetime. This new machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) allows information within a DMP to be fed across stakeholders, linking metadata, repositories, and institutions and allowing for notifications and verification, reporting in real-time. A key goal of this new system is to reduce the burden on researchers by generating automated updates to a plan and facilitating seamless integration with systems and groups that support research.

Linking outputs to DMPs

To support the work of the FAIR Workflows project, the DMP Tool team implemented DMP-related output linking. This new feature allows researchers to follow up on their plans for output sharing by appending publicly shared outputs to the DMP. When researchers provide the resource type and the DOI of the output, the integration links the output to the DMP by creating a [relatedIdentifier element](#) in the DMP ID (DataCite DOI) metadata, defining the relation type, related identifier string, and the identifier type with the metadata [update API call](#).

This integration allows researchers to track their data-sharing activities based on the DMP throughout their project lifecycle and connect outputs to the DMP, even when the output-sharing platform does not support the functionality of linking related works.

The DMP Tool has an engaged community of active users who provide valuable feedback on desired features and how to best implement them. By continually involving this community, especially at key points in the design process, the DMP Tool team stays closely aligned with user needs during development. Frequent user input helps guide the creation of new features that solve real-world problems. Maintaining an open dialogue with the DMP Tool's diverse user base is crucial for building a tool that meets the evolving requirements of the community.

Integration design strategy

From the DMP Tool's perspective, there are two ways a system can approach the implementation of PIDs and related workflows: 1) use them as a connection with another system (e.g. DMP Tool records ORCID iDs) or 2) as the maintainer of a PID (e.g. DMP Tool assigns DOIs to a DMP).

When connecting to PIDs maintained by an external system:

- Verify the system's retention and access policies (will a PID always be resolvable), if not how will your application handle that?
- Make sure that the PIDs are either URLs or at least have a namespace so that you can ensure uniqueness (e.g. an external system may use the id HEWG94HG49G4G which is unique for that system but not globally unique)
- Make sure you understand how they manage versioning. Some systems have different PIDs for each version while others always return the latest version of the object

When assigning and maintaining PIDs through your application:

- Make sure you clearly document your retention and access policies (e.g. are they publicly available 24x7, can the objects they resolve to be embargoed or restricted, etc.)
- Make sure your PIDs are resolvable in the browser
- Make sure you support versioning and then clearly document how that works
- Consider using a system like Crossref or DataCite to register your PIDs so that they become part of the larger DOI ecosystem

Documentation

Feature description and user workflow: Users can upload data management and sharing plans to the application. Uploading a plan assigns it a unique DMP ID (DataCite DOI) and allows tracking of research outputs associated with the work described in the plan.

Feature release documentation:

<https://blog.dmptool.org/2023/01/12/latest-dmptool-release/>

DMPTool Build your Data Management Plan My Dashboard Create Plan Funder Requirements Public DMPs Help

Xiaoli Chen Language Admin

DataCite (datacite.org) DataCite (datacite.org) Email DataCite

FAIR Workflows Project - Attribute Amnesia and Consciousness

Project Details Collaborators Write Plan Research outputs Finalize Download Follow-Up

Funding Outcome

Funding status
Funded

Grant number/url
https://doi.org/10.54224/20568

Save funding information

Research Outputs

Link this plan to research outputs the project has generated – such as journal articles, preprints, datasets, data papers, and software. You can link in-press or embargoed work if a DOI or other URL-based identifier has been assigned to it.

- Zheng, Zefan, Lucia Melloni, Darinka Trubutschek, and Xiaoli Chen. 2022. "Replicating Attribute Amnesia Effect in the Single-Stimulus Design." [Preregistration]. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/4NF7Q>.
- Zheng, Zefan, and Xiaoli Chen. 2022. "The Pitfalls of Traditional Workflows – with a Silver Lining." <https://doi.org/10.5438/8TA1-ER95>.
- Melloni, Lucia, Zefan Zheng, and Darinka Trubutschek. 2023. "Final Pre-Registration of Online Multi-Feature Experiment." [Preregistration]. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/2P9C6>.
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- Chen, Xiaoli. 2022. "Implementing FAIR Workflows D4.2 Communication Plan." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6302912>.
- Chen, Xiaoli, Lucia Melloni, and Kelly Stathis. 2023. "Implementing FAIR Workflows D2.2 Metadata Template Development for Cognitive Neuroscience Research." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7680999>.
- Chen, Xiaoli, Helena Cousijn, Zefan Zheng, Shawn Ross, Martin Jagerhorn, Martin O'Connor, Maria Praetzelis, and Brian Riley. 2023. "Implementing FAIR Workflows D1.2 Mid-Term Project Report." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683864>.
- Chen, Xiaoli, Helena Cousijn, Kelly Stathis, and Gabriela Mejias. 2022. "Implementing FAIR Workflows D4.1 Dissemination Plan." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034858>.
- Chen, Xiaoli, Helena Cousijn, and Kelly Stathis. 2022. "Implementing FAIR Workflows D1.1 Workflows Specification." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7382642>.

Supplemental information: <http://hdl.handle.net/11366/1970> - No citation available.

Add a research output

Save changes

Figure 8. On the Follow-Up tab of a registered DMP, the user can link outputs to the DMP by entering the DOI and specifying the resource type, a feature supported by DataCite API integration.

Links to documentation online:

<https://github.com/CDLUC3/dmptool/wiki/Uploading-DMPs>

Link to readme: [DMPTool ReactJS Client Readme](#)

Description of code repo: The DMP Tool is a free, open-source, online application that helps researchers create data management plans (DMPs). These plans, or DMPs, are now

required by many funding agencies as part of the grant proposal submission process. The DMP Tool provides a click-through wizard for creating a DMP that complies with funder requirements. It also has direct links to funder websites, help text for answering questions, and resources for best practices surrounding data management.

How to reuse the DMPTool open source code: [Installation and Setup instructions](#)

Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval²

The Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval (CEDAR) was established in 2014 to create a computational ecosystem for the development, evaluation, use, and refinement of biomedical metadata. CEDAR focuses on the use of *metadata templates*, which define the data elements needed to describe particular types of biomedical experiments. CEDAR hosts a library of such templates to help scientists create high-quality metadata.

CEDAR provides an end-to-end process that enables:

- Community-based organizations to collaborate to create metadata templates;
- Investigators or curators to use the templates to define the metadata for individual experiments; and
- Scientists to search the metadata to access and analyze the corresponding online datasets.

CEDAR provides a template-based metadata authoring workflow. Template authors use a web-based tool called the Template Designer to create templates, which describe metadata about scientific experiments. These metadata templates are used by a tool called the Metadata Editor to automatically generate form-based interfaces that scientists use to create metadata. The acquired metadata are then stored as *metadata instances* in a Metadata Repository. CEDAR also provides a Workspace that can be used to curate and manage metadata, with analysis capabilities to evaluate the quality of metadata in a repository.

Metadata for the metadata artifacts

Goal of PID integration

The goal of the integration is to allow CEDAR users to create DOIs for metadata templates and instances. Within the CEDAR Workspace, users will be able to request a DOI for templates and instances that they own. CEDAR uses DataCite services to register the requested DOIs. This functionality provides the ability to publish CEDAR metadata

² <https://metadatacenter.org/>

templates and metadata instances and make them visible via DataCite's search capabilities.

Features supporting PID workflows

An array of extensions were made to the CEDAR system to support the creation of DOIs for metadata templates and metadata instances:

1. Interactive menus were provided within the web-based CEDAR Workspace to allow users to request DOIs for templates and instances;
2. A web-based extension was developed to CEDAR to present a DataCite DOI request form to users, which they could then use to provide the metadata necessary to acquire a DOI for the associated template or instance;
3. A new CEDAR microservice was developed to mediate requests from the CEDAR front end to DataCite REST APIs;
4. The core CEDAR repository model was extended to associate DOIs with templates and instances, and
5. Modifications were made to the CEDAR Workspace to present DOIs for templates and instances.

The integration provides CEDAR users with the capability to create DOIs for their metadata templates and metadata instances. A key feature of this integration is that CEDAR users can only create DOIs for templates if they have been published and assigned a version number within the CEDAR system itself. This restriction will encourage users to create DOIs only for completed templates rather than for incomplete metadata artifacts.

The microservice to mediate requests between CEDAR and DataCite REST APIs was developed to be extendable to provide mediation capabilities for other PID registration systems. CEDAR therefore has a starting point for developing additional integrations with 3rd-party PID registration services.

Documentation

Feature description and user workflow: The integration enables CEDAR users to request DOIs for templates and instances by following these steps:

1. Verify that the template or instance is published and versioned within the CEDAR system.
2. Select the "Create DOI using DataCite" menu option in the CEDAR Workspace.
3. Edit a CEDAR DataCite template on the newly opened page, providing the metadata for the template or instance.
4. Choose either "Save Draft" or "Create DOI" at the bottom of the page. Opting for "Save Draft" allows users to continue editing the CEDAR DataCite template later. If "Save Draft" is selected, a draft DOI is generated for the selected CEDAR template or

instance. Subsequently, the draft DOI is updated to a findable DOI when "Create a DOI" is selected later.

The following screenshot displays the "Create DOI using DataCite" option in the CEDAR Workspace.

Figure 1. Create DOI option in metadata artifact additional options menu on CEDAR workbench.

Additionally, the screenshot below shows the CEDAR DataCite template that users must fill out. The system pre-populates default values such as the DOI Prefix, URL (representing the OpenView URL of the template or instance), Publication Year, Publisher, and Resource Type.

↑ CEDAR Bridging - Datacite Create Instance ⊞

DataCite V4.4

Expand All Collapse All

Prefix of DOI*

URL*

Creators (1 .. ∞)

Titles (1 .. ∞)

Publication Year*

Publisher*

Resource Type*

Template
 Instance

Subjects (0 .. ∞)

Contributors (0 .. ∞)

Dates (0 .. ∞)

Language

Alternate Identifiers (0 .. ∞)

Related Identifiers (0 .. ∞)

Sizes (0 .. ∞) No instances yet

Formats (0 .. ∞) No instances yet

Version

Rights (0 .. ∞)

Descriptions (0 .. ∞)

Geographic Location (0 .. ∞)

Funding References (0 .. ∞)

Related Items (0 .. ∞)

JSON-LD - Instance

JSON Schema - Template

Close
Create DOI
Save Draft

Figure 2. DOI metadata submission form on the CEDAR workbench.

If a draft was saved previously, a notification will appear at the top of the page, allowing users to resume editing the previously saved metadata.

Figure 3. Notification for previously drafted DOI metadata.

Technical documentation of the CEDAR integration is available on GitHub:

- Full documentation of the CEDAR platform: [CEDAR Installation Instructions](#)
- Documentation of the DOI creation feature
 - Frontend GitHub repo: [cedar-bridging](#)
 - Backend GitHub repo: [cedar-bridge-server](#)

The cedar-bridge-server contains two subdirectories:

- cedar-bridge-server-core: Core microservice functionality
- cedar-bridge-server-application: Dropwizard-based REST interface to the microservice

Dryad

Dryad is a pioneering research data repository platform designed to facilitate the storage, sharing, and access of research data across various scientific disciplines. Emphasizing the principles of Open Science, Dryad provides a robust infrastructure that allows researchers globally to upload, share, and access a wide range of data types. The platform is specifically tailored to enhance the visibility and impact of research data by ensuring it is discoverable, reusable, and citable.

One of Dryad's key features is its integration with journals and funding agencies, streamlining the process of data deposition in line with publication and research funding requirements. This integration ensures that research data is not only preserved but also linked to the corresponding research articles, enhancing the transparency and reproducibility of scientific findings. Dryad's contribution to the FAIR Workflows project pushed this integration one step further: the integration between Dryad and CEDAR module create meaningful link between research data and domain-specific metadata that put the datasets into human and machine readable context, facilitating reuse in the long-term.

Enriching open datasets with domain-specific metadata

Dryad has integrated the CEDAR Embeddable Editor component, enabling researchers to select and fill out appropriate metadata templates during the data deposition process. When researchers select a template and complete the form, the discipline-specific

metadata created will be saved and made publicly available alongside the datasets being deposited. Additionally, when a researcher selects a template to accompany the data deposition, Dryad will include the DOI of the template in the dataset's DOI metadata as a related identifier.

The integration is currently implemented on Dryad stage instance. The official launch of the new feature is planned for early 2024, pending accessibility improvements on UX/UI elements.

Goal of integration

The goal of integrating CEDAR embeddable editor component is to encourage the effective usage of domain-specific metadata in the data management and data sharing workflows. Making domain community endorsed template reusable for the community through integration rewards template authors and increase their impact and reach, at the same time providing the option for researchers to attach disciplinary metadata will enrich the contextual information for the datasets and ultimately improve their reusability.

Feature supporting PID integration

Data description

Standardized metadata

Fill out a standardized metadata form for your discipline to make your data more useful to others.

Choose a metadata form

Templeton Draft for Neuroscience Data ▾ + Add Metadata Form

Subject keywords: * Adding keywords improves the findability of your dataset. E.g. scientific names, method type

Figure 9. Users will have the opportunity to choose relevant metadata form (template) in a drop down menu in the Data Description section of the data submission form.

Figure 10. The CEDAR Embeddable Editor module will render the form in the same window, without sending the user to a different website, breaking the workflow.

Human Cognitive Neuroscience Data

Expand All Collapse All

About the template
Click to read the instruction

Dataset ?
Use this section to capture domain-specific information about the dataset, including data modality, acquisition technique, processing stage, domain standards used to arrange and annotate the data, and access information about source data, if available.

Data acquisition technique (Neural data)

Preprocessing(1 .. ∞)

Standard(1 .. ∞)

Source dataset(1 .. ∞)

Experiment

Analysis

Crediting and Acknowledgement

Further information

SAVE

JSON-LD - Instance

Figure 11. The form can be expanded and folded based on the arrangement of the template components, complete with the ability to save the metadata record to the dataset.

Documentation

Technical documentation of Dryad’s CEDAR embeddable editor module integration can be found on GitHub:

https://github.com/CDL-Dryad/dryad-app/blob/main/documentation/external_services/cedar_embeddable_editor.md

ChronosHub

Enabling streamlined data sharing

ChronosHub is a leading Open Access management platform and serves to manage all types of Open Access, including processing of OA fees (gold/hybrid), OA agreement monitoring (gold/hybrid), and full-text deposits (green) into connected repositories.

The platform serves to unburden researchers and library staff from administrative tasks along the publishing journey by automating data collection, communication, and reporting through integrations and AI scanning of manuscripts and invoices. Institutions, consortia, funders, and publishers subscribe to one or several modules on the platform and use it to drive their OA and Open Science strategy.

Goal of PID integrations

Workflow automation is the essence of the ChronosHub platform and to achieve automation, the ChronosHub platform needs to integrate with all kinds of systems across the ecosystem. The most important prerequisite for a seamless integration is that ChronosHub, but also other systems, applies the FAIR principles as far as possible. First of all, the systems need to offer an API to technically enable a machine-to-machine exchange. Secondly, PIDs for all the relevant entities that are being exchanged between the ChronosHub platform and these other systems are a must, as anything else requires manual validation.

Features supporting PID integration

ChronosHub makes use of Ringgold and ROR IDs for all organizations on the platform. This enables integrations to present organizational affiliations and support accurate input in a seamless workflow for researchers/authors/grantees.

There is an integration with ORCID to enable users to make use of their ORCID iDs on ChronosHub.

ChronosHub uses Crossref DOIs to enrich records on the platform once the output has been published.

What metadata/PIDs are created/enriched through the integration

Through the FAIR Workflows project, ChronosHub now also integrates with DataCite API to find DMPs and datasets that authors can associate with their research articles and other outputs. The platform uses the authors' ORCID iDs to automatically locate any matching datasets in DataCite.

Through the FAIR Workflows project, ChronosHub now also supports direct deposit into the Dryad data repository. When researchers submit an article through ChronosHub, they

can now simultaneously deposit the accompanying dataset via ChronosHub to the Dryad platform and thus link the research article to other research outputs.

This means that the datasets and DMPs get connected and enrich the following other entities:

- Authors (and their affiliations)
- Grants (and their funders)
- Research outputs (and their journals and publishers)

Integration design strategy

The ChronosHub team built the integrations with DataCite and Dryad in a modular way. This means the functionality can be reused at any point along the publishing workflow, whether it's at manuscript submission, article acceptance or after an article has been published.

The integration was designed to be as easy and intuitive as possible for users, including automated lookups against DataCite based on the authors' ORCID iDs.

The design is flexible enough to cater to any further repository integrations if any institutions, funders, or publishers have other preferences than Dryad.

The metadata is structured and can be exported into MS Excel or reused directly over ChronosHub's APIs.

Documentation

Authors can use the new feature on the ChronosHub platform upon manuscript submission, article acceptance, and after the article has been published. They can either associate an existing dataset or DMP with their research output or deposit a new dataset directly into Dryad and get it associated with the research output.

The workflow is:

- 1) Confirm if any of the found matching datasets should be associated with the research output.
- 2) Use the search to find and associate any matching datasets (with DataCite DOIs) with the research output (on ChronosHub).
- 3) Deposit a new dataset directly into Dryad by clicking 'Deposit', and then confirm (or first uploading the actual datasets). Dryad automatically creates a DataCite DOI that is linked to the manuscript/article on ChronosHub.

The screenshot below includes the new section for finding or depositing datasets. Associated datasets are automatically linked with the grant, grantee, and all the other indirectly related entities (organizations, journals, publishers, etc.).

Datasets

Please link all relevant deposited datasets to your article submission here. If a dataset is not already deposited, you can do this as part of the flow.

Selected Datasets

No datasets selected. Add datasets from suggestions, or use the search feature to find relevant datasets.

Suggestions Based on Author ORCIDs

- + **Aryl bis-sulfonamides bind to the active site of a h...**
10.17863/cam.32753
- + **First Atmospheric Measurements and Emission E...**
10.5281/zenodo.8118903
- + **First Atmospheric Measurements and Emission E...**
10.5281/zenodo.8118904

Search Datasets (by title or DOI)

Want to deposit your dataset?

If you haven't deposited the dataset yet, you can do so as part of this flow. Upon deposit, the dataset will automatically be added to the list of selected datasets.

[Deposit a dataset here](#)

[Save as draft](#)

[Submit your manuscript](#)

Figure 4. Dataset section of the data submission form on ChronosHub.

Datasets

Please link all relevant deposited datasets to your article submission here. If a dataset is not already deposited, you can do this as part of the flow.

Selected Datasets

No datasets selected. Add datasets from suggestions, or use the search feature to find relevant datasets.

No Suggested Datasets

Did you add the manuscript title or author ORCIDiDs to enable possible dataset suggestions?

Search Datasets (by title or DOI)

10.25434/croce-riccardo_phd2021

Functionalization of Black Phosphorus with Inorganic Reagents
10.25434/vanni-matteo_phd2021

Complexation Thermodynamics of Cucurbit[6]uril with Aliphatic Alcohols, Amines, and Diamines
10.34804/supra.20210928377

Nitrile N-oxides and nitrile imines as electrophilic partners for the discovery of novel isocyanide multicomponent reactions: an innovative strategy for the synthesis of molecular scaffolds useful in medicinal chemistry
10.20373/unupo/opentesis/86920

Figure 5. Searching for openly shared datasets by title or DOI using DataCite API integration.

Datasets

Please link all relevant deposited datasets to your article submission here. If a dataset is not already deposited, you can do this as part of the flow.

Selected Datasets

Functionalization of Black Phosphorus with Inorg...
10.25434/vanni-matteo_phd2021
🗑️

Investigation of inorganic nanocrystals as electro...
10.15167/chen-lin_phd2018-03-15
🗑️

Binding of inorganic and organic cations by p-sulf...
10.34804/supra.20210928275
🗑️

Suggestions Based on Manuscript Title

+
SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NEW ...
10.13130/tordin-elisa_phd2010-12-10

+
Functionalization of Black Phosphorus with Inorg...
10.25434/vanni-matteo_phd2021

+
Binding of inorganic cations by p-sulfonatocalix[4...
10.34804/supra.20210928275

+
Organic and inorganic data of ODP Hole 177-1088B
10.1594/pangaea.924480

Suggestions Based on Author ORCIDs

+
New DataCite Metadata Updates Support Softwar...
10.5438/nzhx-xx96

+
EZID DOI Service is Evolving
10.5438/0x88-gvge

Search Datasets (by title or DOI)

Start typing to search

Want to deposit your dataset?

If you haven't deposited the dataset yet, you can do so as part of this flow. Upon deposit, the dataset will automatically be added to the list of selected datasets.

Figure 6. Adding related dataset suggestions based on manuscript title and author ORCID IDs.

Want to deposit your dataset?

Just follow the simple steps below to deposit a dataset and add it to your manuscript submission.

Where do you want to deposit you dataset?

Dryad

Deposit dataset with Dryad

Depositing your dataset with Dryad is a two-step process. First you **create the dataset entry** with metadata gathered from your submission form. Then you **upload your dataset file(s)** to attach them to the created entry.

Your dataset entry will be created with the following metadata:

- Title**
This is the manuscript title
- Authors**
Jessica Doe (0000-0002-7285-027X)
- Abstract**
This is the manuscript abstract ...
- Keywords**
-

Create Dataset Entry with Dryad

Figure 7. Depositing a dataset via the Dryad integration.

As an integral part of the commercially available platform, the ChronosHub integration code repositories are not publicly accessible. However, the team is happy to share their knowledge and welcomes inquiries from interested parties and future integrators.

Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)

A Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is a globally unique, persistent identifier (PID) for research projects and activities. It comprises both a RAiD name containing the unique persistent identifier prefix '10.25', and a RAiD metadata record³.

The strength of RAiD is its flexibility to link activities on different levels to capture research workflows in a more granular manner, i.e. a research project will include two complementary studies/experiments, and each experiment will be preceded by a series of pilot experiments.

In the FAIR Workflows project, the RAiD team at the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) worked with DataCite to explore the metadata properties to be included in the RAiD

³ <https://raid.org/overview>

metadata schema to support the RAiD use cases, and the implementation of a metadata exchange mechanism that supports the interoperability of RAiD with the PID Graph.

Building interoperability into RAiD metadata schema

The RAiD Metadata Schema, developed by ARDC, is a structured framework designed to standardize and organize data elements associated with RAiD names. It facilitates the identification, creation, updating, and tracking of RAiD metadata records, playing a crucial role in linking various research activities.

Incorporating insights from the FAIR Workflows project the RAiD team referenced the DataCite Metadata Schema to promote interoperability with the broader scholarly infrastructure. This alignment allows for seamless integration with systems and standards prevalent in academia and research, enhancing the utility of RAiDs in diverse research contexts, especially in multi-faceted fields like neuroscience.

The RAiD schema supports the FAIR principles by enabling standardized identification and comprehensive metadata management. It comprises core, extended, and local components, each serving specific roles while maintaining flexibility for adapting to the diverse needs of the research community. This approach ensures that RAiD can effectively link varied research activities and outputs, promoting collaboration, data discovery, and reuse, thereby accelerating scientific innovation and discovery.

Core Metadata Schema Properties	Extended Metadata Schema Properties
1. Identifier 1.1. identifier.id 1.2. identifier.schemaUri 1.3. identifier.registrationAgency 1.3.1. identifier.registrationAgency.id 1.3.2. identifier.registrationAgency.schemaUri 1.4. identifier.owner 1.4.1. identifier.owner.id 1.4.2. identifier.owner.schemaUri 1.4.3. identifier.owner.servicePoint 1.5. identifier.license 1.6. identifier.version 2. Date 2.1. date.startDate 2.2. date.endDate 3. Title 3.1. title.text 3.2. title.type	12. Subject 12.1. subject.id 12.2. subject.schemaUri 12.3. subject.keyword 12.3.1. subject.keyword.text 12.3.2. subject.keyword.language 12.3.2.1. subject.keyword.language.id 12.3.2.2. subject.keyword.language.schemaUri 13. TraditionalKnowledgeLabel 13.1. traditionalKnowledgeLabel.id 13.2. traditionalKnowledgeLabel.schemaUri 14. SpatialCoverage 14.1. spatialCoverage.id 14.2. spatialCoverage.schemaUri 14.3. spatialCoverage.place 14.3.1. spatialCoverage.place.text 14.3.2. spatialCoverage.place.language

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.2.1. title.type.id 3.2.2. title.type.schemaUri 3.3. title.language <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.3.1. title.language.id 3.3.2. title.language.schemaUri 3.4. title.startDate 3.5. title.endDate 4. Description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1. description.text 4.2. description.type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.2.1. description.type.id 4.2.2. description.type.schemaUri 4.3. description.language <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.3.1. description.language.id 4.3.2. description.language.schemaUri 5. Contributor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1. contributor.id 5.2. contributor.schemaUri 5.3. contributor.position <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.3.1. contributor.position.id 5.3.2. contributor.position.schemaUri 5.3.3. contributor.position.startDate 5.3.4. contributor.position.endDate 5.4. contributor.leader 5.5. contributor.contact 5.6. contributor.role <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.6.1. contributor.role.id 5.6.2. contributor.role.schemaUri 6. Organisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6.1. organisation.id 6.2. organisation.schemaUri 6.3. organisation.role <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6.3.1. organisation.role.id 6.3.2. organisation.role.schemaUri 6.3.3. organisation.role.startDate 6.3.4. organisation.role.endDate 7. RelatedObject <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7.1. relatedObject.id 7.2. relatedObject.schemaUri 7.3. relatedObject.type 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 14.3.2.1. spatialCoverage.place.language.id 14.3.2.2. spatialCoverage.place.language.schemaUri
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7.3.1. relatedObject.type.id 7.3.2. relatedObject.type.schemaUri 7.4. relatedObject.category 7.4.1. relatedObject.category.id 7.4.2. relatedObject.category.schemaUri 8. AlternateIdentifier 8.1. alternateIdentifier.id 8.2. alternateIdentifier.type 9. AlternateUrl 9.1. alternateUrl.url 10. RelatedRaid 10.1. relatedRaid.id 10.2. relatedRaid.type 10.2.1. relatedRaid.type.id 10.2.2. relatedRaid.type.schemaUri 11. Access 11.1. access.type 11.1.1. access.type.id 11.1.2. access.type.schemaUri 11.2. access.embargoExpiry 11.3. access.statement 11.3.1. access.statement.text 11.3.2. access.statement.language 11.3.2.1. access.statement.language.id 11.3.2.2. access.statement.language.schemaUri	
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Table 1. Overview of the RAiD metadata schema core and extended properties.

RAiD metadata will be incorporated into the PID Graph through planned integration with DataCite, providing the community with the ability to search connections between RAiDs and DataCite DOIs. This integration is part of an ongoing collaboration between RAiD and DataCite, aimed at enriching the PID Graph with enhanced project-level metadata, making research more FAIR.

Documentation

- The full RAiD metadata schema can be accessed here: <https://metadata.raid.org/>
- User documentation can be accessed here: <https://documentation.raid.org/raid/>
- Architecture: The high-level system architecture is documented on Github: <https://github.com/au-research/raido/blob/main/doc/architecture/raid-architecture.md>

- The ARDC RAiD service is deployed in AWS, and the operational environment is documented in Github:
<https://github.com/au-research/raido/blob/main/doc/architecture/environment/operational-environment.md>
- Environment: RAiD provides both an API (<https://github.com/au-research/raido/blob/main/api-svc/idl-raid-v2/src/raido-stable-v1.yaml>) and a web interface (<https://documentation.raid.org/raid/raid-user-interface-documentation>). There are test, demo, and production environments. The demo environment has a Swagger UI available for experimentation:
<https://api.demo.raid.org.au/swagger-ui.html>

Future work

The integrations built in the project provide excellent examples for the versatile technological latitude of the existing open scholarly infrastructure and how tools and platforms can take advantage of the variety of integration options available to bolster their system and plug into the wider ecosystem of persistent identifiers and open metadata. Equipped with the experience gained in this project, we summarize and present the next steps toward more prevalent adoption of PID integrations across different service platforms, focusing on the one step up on the strategy for culture change - making it easy, for both service integrators and the researchers.

Figure 12. Open Science Framework strategy for culture change⁴

Making it easy for integrators

Educational Materials on Open Infrastructure

⁴ <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>

There is a significant need for more readily available and comprehensive educational resources on open infrastructure, including guides, tutorials, more comprehensive documentation and best practice case studies. These resources are necessary to inform and educate integrators about the nuances of open infrastructure, including its benefits, how to best leverage it, and how to navigate its challenges. By enhancing understanding and knowledge, educational materials can drive more efficient and impactful integration efforts.

Streamlining API Interactions

One of the key steps moving forward is to simplify the way various systems interact through APIs. This involves creating more straightforward, well-documented APIs that can easily be understood and utilized by new integrators. Simplifying these interactions will not only make the integration process more efficient, but also encourage broader participation and collaboration from various platforms.

Unified Metadata Standards

Another critical task is the harmonization of metadata standards across different platforms. Currently, disparate metadata schemas can create barriers to effective data exchange and integration. Establishing unified, commonly accepted metadata standards will ensure a smoother interoperability between various systems, enhancing the overall utility and effectiveness of the PID integrations.

Integration Testing and Validation Tools

To ensure that new integrations are robust and effective, there is a need for dedicated tools and frameworks to test and validate these integrations. These tools would help integrators to reliably assess the performance and reliability of their systems in a controlled environment, significantly reducing the risk of errors and incompatibilities in live deployments.

Making it easy for researchers

User-Friendly Interfaces

A major focus for making integrations more accessible to researchers is user experience. The goal is to make these interfaces intuitive and easy to navigate, thereby lowering the learning curve for researchers and enabling them to leverage these tools more effectively in their work.

Automated Metadata Capture

To further ease the burden on researchers, developing capabilities for automated metadata capture is essential. This would mean less manual data entry, reducing the potential for errors, and saving valuable time for researchers. Automated systems can pull relevant information from interconnected platforms, streamlining workflows.

Training and Support Materials

Given the diversity of FAIR supporting platforms involved, there is a significant need for comprehensive training materials and support resources for researchers. These materials would help researchers understand how to best utilize these integrated systems, addressing common queries and fit FAIR practices into their workflows.

Community involvement

Finally, establishing a robust user feedback mechanism through community building is crucial. This would provide researchers with a direct channel to report issues, suggest improvements, and share their experiences. Such feedback is invaluable for continuous improvement of the systems, ensuring they remain aligned with the evolving needs of the research community.